

ANALYSIS OF THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES IN LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE

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Annotation

This following article makes analysis of Uzbek and English languages in Linguistic Competence. Author researched other Scientific works about on this topic. And she analysis all works. After that she put an aim for this field. Finally it was established a new results and methods by analyzing Uzbek and English languages.

Keywords: Linguistic Competence, analysis, aim, objectives, life process, teaching methods.

According to N. Chomsky, language competence is an ideal grammatical science, always associated with knowledge of the system language [1]. And the American scientist D. Himes presents a point of view somewhat different from the opinion of N. Chomsky. He notes: "There are rules of use, without them there is no benefit from grammatical rules" [2]. Language competence is a complex psychological system, it includes, in addition to information about the language being studied in the learning process, and the speech experience of everyday communication, and on its basis - the feeling of language. In the context of modern education in the theory of learning, how. The analysis of the development of the concept of linguistic competence shows that this term means a set of linguistic knowledge and skills that make it possible to speak another language in accordance with the linguistic norm that is accepted in various fields of activity. It also helps to develop the language abilities of the trainees [3]. This knowledge is reflected in grammar, they tell about the appearance in the language, by changing the initial construction, structures of all possible forms of sentences, as well as about the grammatical relationships within a sentence and between sentences. Here the main goal for the student is the ability to use the studied language as a means of communication. In the language Competencies Each student should have their own vocabulary.

In order to improve students' knowledge in practice, the formation of types of language competence is required [4]. To do this, the following actions should be performed:

- 1) study the problems of language competence formation;
- 2) development of the structure of language competence;
- 3) clarifying the state of students' language competence in various learning environments;
- 4) development of techniques and methods for the formation of students' language competence and the definition of conditions;
- 5) checking the effectiveness of the named conditions of the form-knowledge of language competence.

These actions are carried out in several steps. The first step is to determine the level of knowledge in this field. The second stage is the development of new curricula for teaching Uzbek as a foreign language and the preparation of assignments for teaching. The third stage is the derivation of research results and their practical use [5].

Building language competence is one of the most important aspects of teaching a native language, since language competence means the ability of students to use words, their various forms, syntactic constructions in accordance with the norms of the literary language, the

ability to use synonymous means language, after all, is the ability to be able to use all the riches of language[6]. Language competence is a psychological system that includes the formation of a linguistic sense based on the experience of everyday conversational communication and the establishment of a special language learning process. Currently, special importance is attached to the construction of language competence, since it is regarded as a prerequisite for the formation of a socially active person. Successful mastery of learning methods The language is provided with a high level of linguistic competence. Language competence allows you to adequately perceive someone else's speech, recognize the intonation and modality of the interlocutor's speech, evaluate someone else's speech, and provides the ability to give appropriate answers based on the socio-cultural context. Language competence is often considered as the position of the necessary specific skills required for speech communication between members of society and understanding it as a language academic discipline. Language competence is based on the innate linguistic category and the student's ability to construct grammar.

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